

Teachers Leadership Dimension in History Learning

Lee Bih Ni, Zulfhikar Rabe, Nurul Asyikin Hassan

Abstract—The Ministry of Education Malaysia dynamically and drastically made the subject of History mandatory to be in force in 2013. This is in recognition of the nation's heritage and treasures in maintaining true facts and information for future generations of the State. History reveals the civilization of a nation and the fact of national cultural heritage. Civilization needs to be preserved as a legacy of sovereign heritage. Today's generation is the catalyst for future heirs who will support the principle and direction of the country. In line with the National Education Philosophy that aims to shape the potential development of individuals holistically and uniquely in order to produce a balanced and harmonious student in terms of intellectual, spiritual, emotional and physical. Hence, understanding the importance of studying the history subject as a pillar of identity and the history of nationhood is to be a priority in the pursuit of knowledge and empowering the spirit of statehood that is nurtured through continuous learning at school. Judging from the aspect of teacher leadership role in integrating history in a combined way based on Teacher Education Philosophy. It empowers the teaching profession towards the teacher to support noble character. It also supports progressive and scientific views. Teachers are willing to uphold the State's aspirations and celebrate the country's cultural heritage. They guarantee individual development and maintain a united, democratic, progressive and disciplined society. Teacher's role as a change and leadership agent in education begins in the classroom through formal or informal educational processes. This situation is expanded in schools, communities and countries. The focus of this paper is on the role of teacher leadership influencing the effectiveness of teaching and learning history in the classroom environment. Leadership guides to teachers' perceptions on the role of teacher leadership, teaching leadership, and the teacher leadership role and effective teacher leadership role. Discussions give emphasis on aspects of factors affecting the classroom environment, forming the classroom agenda, effective classroom implementation methods, suitable climate for historical learning and teacher challenges in implicating the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes.

Keywords—Teacher leadership, leadership lessons, effective classroom, effective teacher.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the development of leadership role issues in education, many studies have been conducted on principals' leadership [5], [15], as opposed to the role of teacher leadership in the classroom. According to Banathy [1], systemic change is any change that occurs in a part of an organizational system that affects the whole organization, and consequently, will bring new changes to the organization. When this systemic change

is linked to the role of teacher leadership, understanding the role of teacher leadership is a unit that will affect the overall effectiveness of a school. The difference in achievement of pupils in the school was also influenced by the significant differences in the teachers who contributed to the excellence of the school.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Review Stage

Generally, the teacher has the perception that the role of teacher leadership lies on the shoulders of principals or school administrators. The foundation of a school's success is not due to the leader of the teaching being principals or teachers only but is encouraged by the coordination and collaboration of teachers as teaching leaders, while principals are the coordinators or administrators [14]. Teachers assume their role as only teaches of students according to the provided syllabus. They are technically sure that the allocated curriculum needs to be spent on a given time frame. Teachers are important change agents in ensuring their schools become effective schools [14].

B. Teacher Leadership Role Definition

Pilot [7] defines leadership as a business or action affecting others by informally aiming to achieve the desired goal. Good leadership will always bring positive change to the party. Drath and Palus (in [21]) say leadership is the process of accepting what others do in common with which people will understand and be committed. Southworth [18], defining the role of teacher leadership as related to teaching and learning, including teacher professional learning as well as student development. De Bevoise [7] pointed out that the role of teacher leadership is the actions taken by a principal or entrusted parties to promote learning growth among pupils. Therefore, teachers should be careful about teaching and learning, including the learning of their profession as well as the development of the students themselves. Based on some of the above definitions, leadership is an art or process that affects human activities related to their duties and responsibilities. Their involvement is voluntarily and strives towards the effectiveness and achievement of organizational goals. When leadership is discussed from an educational perspective, it is often associated with the role of teacher leadership in school and the classroom.

Hook and Vass [10] define the role of classroom teacher leadership as a skill in which the teacher uses a leadership style for his or her own skills and communicates with others. In addition, this skill is an ability to relate what happens every day with two-party interactions. This skill is also the ability of a teacher to deliver a vision to the students and to convince

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and influence them. The role of teacher leadership exists in the context of students acquiring information or input. They do not realize they can achieve in every classroom when there is a positive development that directly affects their personality. When a teacher raises a hand during a lesson, all the students in the classroom become silent; as this is accepted as a signal and they expect guidance or an example from a teacher. According to Hook and Vass [10], the role of effective teacher leadership requires teachers who have the skills to develop the ability to understand and have vision. They need to have effective linkage skills. They need to understand the behavior and desires of their students. They also need to understand the classroom is a system and be able to find solutions and analyze information.

In order to produce effective teaching, Fenstermacher and Soltis [8] suggest three approaches, namely the Executive Approach; Empathy Approach; and the Liberal Approach. The process of teaching and learning normally occurs in the classroom where pupils follow the teaching are respondents and the teachers are acting as leaders. Meaningful learning is always associated with the quality of the role of teacher leadership. It can be successful in encouraging, acting as a mentor, and able to influence pupils to strive to achieve learning objectives. Its implementation can be achieved during the teaching and learning process in the classroom by referring to efforts that have been directed towards the achievement of learning outcomes according to the topic being taught. The success of teachers as leaders will be evident in their ability to make changes in the classroom through collaboration with students towards the achievement of teaching and learning goals. The role of teacher leadership is also associated with people capable of planning, directing, controlling the process of travel and forming strategies for achieving goals. Therefore, the leader should be capable and able to change the subordinate attitude to drive towards achieving goals.

C. Teachers' Perception of the Role of Teacher Leadership

Synonymously, teachers have the perception that the role of teacher leadership lies in the head of the principal or school administrator. According to Blase and Blase [2], the foundation of a school's success is not due to the teaching leader, principals or teachers. The foundation of success is driven by coordination and collaboration of teachers and principals; teachers as teaching leaders, while principals are the coordinators or administrators. Teachers assume that their role is only to teach students according to the provided syllabus. They ensure that the allocated curriculum needs to be spent on a set period of time. Sparks [19] argues that teachers are important change agents in ensuring their schools become effective schools.

The general goal of teacher leadership is to add value (value added) or to maintain conditions that promote student learning atmosphere. The skill and competence of the teacher leadership role practiced by a school administrator should have the term shared or delegated to the teachers involved in the teaching and learning process. In addition, the school administration should take care of leading teachers towards

excellence in teaching and learning programs. Teaching and management issues include teacher and pupil assessment, school climate, curriculum and co-curriculum, teaching resources, tools, and decision-making. Teachers need to be given the necessary skills to meet short and long term goals, community support, communication and interaction between principals as school administrators. Studies show that in the process of teaching teacher programs, the role of educators as the role of teacher leadership requires the efficacy of educational techniques and academic excellence that can be implemented in the form of effective strategies. Education is not static and often fluctuating such as complex education programs, increased professionalism and specialization of teachers, the introduction of educational technology as a source of teaching and learning, community and parental expectations, and curriculum changes. This will all create new demands that should be taken into account in realizing the role of teacher leadership.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this paper, narrative literature is used to describe the current state of both art and science in the focus. The researcher used a literary narrative research to build the foundation of scientific knowledge, and collected all the important points in the discussion and put them in here with reference to the particular field in which this paper was originally based.

IV. FINDINGS

Today, people understand the importance of history, both from a global perspective and in terms of our everyday lives. The days when history was considered a lifeless, irrelevant subject are long gone. History is about who we are and where we came from, and when it comes to bringing the past alive, History teachers are the perfect leader tools for the job.

A. Leadership Role of Teachers Features

According to Shippen and Shippen [16], a teacher who has effective leadership has favored leadership that can build and deliver a clear vision in the classroom [3]. He has the ability to lead and is flexible, as well as transparent [22]. He is able to lead and be an exemplary role model to his students. Teachers intelligently and efficiently make decisions beneficial to students with no prejudice to the interests of the organization [4]. A teacher is scraping selfishness and is instead prioritizing the interests and welfare of the students [16]; although, sometimes he is burdened with conflicts of student discipline problems. Teachers make a balanced judgment and rational aims to avoid the feeling of dissatisfaction among students. They are honest and humble for the purpose of building a transparent and positive relationship between teachers and student [22]. They try to practice continuous learning for the purpose of enhancing and increasing their knowledge and skills. According to Kane [11], knowledge gained by teachers for continuing education will increase the effectiveness of their teaching in the classroom. Consequently, the teaching and learning situation in the classroom is to be more realistic,

systematic and conducted in a controlled manner.

Lashway [13] discussed the leadership role to generate the effectiveness of the teaching and learning of Leading Learning Communities program developed by the National Association of Elementary School Principals (ESP). ESP has redefined the role of teacher leadership to generate the effectiveness of teaching and learning. ESP has also redefined the role of teacher leadership to encourage the students to prioritize efforts to learn, determine the expectations of high achievement, and adjust the content of teaching and learning towards the standard standards. ESP is using a variety of data sources to assess learning and enable the support of the community or stakeholders for the success of the school.

B. Factors Affecting the Classroom Climate

Hook and Vass [10] referred to effective classroom culture by identifying several factors that affect the classroom environment. They find a balance between encouragement and warning, and develop rapport with students, and involve students with aspirations and expectations and maintain perfect working relationship. An effective classroom culture adopts a conducive environment for student learning. Effective class culture requires the participation of students on teacher teaching.

C. Effective Teaching Leaders

Glickman [24] pointed out that the leadership role of the teacher will be able to run efficiently if the leader has three main categories, namely the need to acquire knowledge of the area; tasks and responsibilities; and the need to practice the skills and expertise.

A teacher who teaches the compulsory History subject commands deep knowledge in this field to ensure that the learning process is carried out smoothly. When students ask questions, teachers can give a positive response and meet the needs of students. A teacher's positive response can cultivate the self-confidence of students. When giving assignments to students, teachers should emphasize the goals of each task. The students should also understand the required knowledge of self-discovery. The leadership role of teachers in the classroom requires skill which covers two aspects, namely intrapersonal and interpersonal, as well as technical skills [6]. The intrapersonal and interpersonal skills are an attempt to guess the mood, goals, motivations, and feelings when faced with their students in the learning process. Teachers who master these skills will successfully master the students teaching and learning environment in the classroom. Teachers in the classroom should be sensitive to facial expressions, voice, and the body language of students. The abilities and concerns of teachers recognize and identify the nature of the students in the classroom allows instill a culture of student learning interest. They explore the particular subject of history that emphasizes memorization of facts and understanding as well. In addition, history teachers need to master ICT skills including management and technical teaching aids such as computers, LCD projectors, video, charts, and so on for more interactive and diversity teaching and learning process [12]. At

the same time, teachers can use worksheets and newspaper clippings to assist in the teaching and learning process, making it more conducive and challenging.

According to a study by Porter and Brophy [25], there are seven key determinants of effective teachers. Teachers can form academic balance and socialization of students. They have a mastery of content and in-depth knowledge. They are a model to train students to process information and correct any misconceptions of the facts or content among them. Teachers expand student experiences and project themselves as a reflective teacher.

D. Shaping the Agenda Classroom

Agenda classrooms are very important to determine the implementation plan in the role of teacher leadership. It will establish a classroom climate that is conducive to the academic and social development of students. According to Hook and Vass [10], there are four main keys in the classroom agenda of rights, responsibilities, rules, and routines. When applying leadership theories in the classroom, teachers require a clear response, which can be delivered, and which framed to make a decision on student behavior. It is a framework that can be accepted and understood by the students in a particular situation. The decision should be based on considerations that had been agreed upon and adhered to in terms of the four basic rights of students, namely [10]; students' rights to learn, the rights of teachers to teach, the right of every individual to security aspects, both physically and psychologically, and the right of every individual to a level of respect and veneration.

Based on these rights, effective learning management is the absolute right of the teacher to overcome the problem of concentration of students in the classroom. In the meantime, teachers can meet professional responsibilities as authorities on the protection of individual rights in the security aspect. Students must feel good and secure before undergoing the learning process. Rights and responsibilities are the two things are inseparable. Responsibilities of the role of teacher leadership focus on the behavior of students to make decisions or elections positively [23]. As a teacher, an effort to encourage students to choose responsible behavior towards an effective leadership role of teachers is complicated. Teachers should encourage students to be responsible for the approach and efforts to attain the desired success [20]. Society always emphasizes the importance of rules in schools. During the process of teaching and learning, we need to emphasize the regulations which must be observed by students to ensure that teaching and a learning process on track [17]. Teachers must distinguish between rules and routines.

The first rule is to ensure that teachers can teach and that students can learn in a conducive atmosphere. The role of teacher leadership will be briefed with regards to the rules in the first meeting with the students, touching aspects such as responses to questions, classroom exits, book distributions and teaching materials, the beginning of the lesson and the end of the lesson. Secondly, prescribe the security of physical and psychological safety of school property, and thirdly, guarding the rights in terms of honor and glory. These three rules are a

guide for teachers to ensure that students understand and comply with the requirements of the rules that have been communicated by the school [6]. Routine differs from the rules because it routinely prioritizes the administrative and procedural aspects required so that the classroom atmosphere is well-managed. Routine is a set of behaviors that need to be implemented to help the success of students [12]. In addition, referring to the classroom routine, classroom activities such as marking the arrival of the students' schedule, checking the physical condition of the classroom or laboratory, and distributing teaching materials, as well as collecting and return exercise books and so on.

E. The Skills Required

The ideal climate for learning can be achieved when the teacher is able to ensure that the environment is appropriate to enable the teaching and learning process to run smoothly [23]. In this context, class work and student goals should be clear and easy to understand. Teachers need to promote the classroom as a place of academic learning to achieve the goal of National Education Philosophy. Clear teaching objectives are able to monitor the teaching and learning performance of History in the classroom.

In the process of teaching and learning History, teachers should act in self reflection before, during and after each teaching session. Prior to the teaching session, the teacher should reflect on the planning and prepare to begin teaching. During the teaching process, the teacher should act to maximize all the knowledge and methods of effective delivery in mastering the mood, ambiance and interactive relationship with the students. After the lesson, the teacher can reflect what was done, spoken and planned in the classroom [20]. History teachers are encouraged to write diaries for self-refinement for future reference and correct any mistakes. During the process of teaching and learning, teachers can practice collaborative learning. This means that students are positive and independent, responsible, working in groups and socializing with group members to carry out specific tasks. Next, the student thinks to solve the problem addressed to him. Teachers should determine the appropriate teaching objectives and determine the size of the group, e.g. the heterogeneous group allows each member to have a specific role. In order to reason problem solving, pupils discuss between groups, conduct experimental sessions and find references either from the teacher, books or the Internet. In this context, teachers act as observers and facilitators and assess the student learning process as well as the results of their assignments [20] [23]. With this approach, students have the opportunity to grow according to their ability and self-esteem, especially in exploring the fact-finding or historical sequence of each discovery and activity. At the end of the session, teachers should praise and support and reward the efforts shown by students in their involvement in the active learning process and manipulate the classroom space as an effective interaction resource.

V. CONCLUSION

The Ministry of Malaysia Education and the Malaysian Higher Education Ministry have difficulty in the accurately estimate the number of History teachers based on current needs and the posting of teachers who do not follow the school administrator's request option. Problems exist when there is a demand and lack of teachers, when educators do not have the right specialization to teach specific subjects, when there are larger class sizes, and when intake interviews prospective teachers who are not in the History field, etc. The demand and lack of History option teachers is a barrier to school principals' to maintain the quality of teacher leadership in classroom teaching. This problem undermines the role of effective teacher leadership in the classroom. As a result, principals cannot motivate their teachers towards excellence and effectiveness of teaching and learning that is expected.

A school is a unit of educational organization where teachers need to engage in the role of teacher leadership as well as education leadership. Adhering to the theory, the teacher's responsibility for teaching is to ensure that all their energy and efforts are aimed at delivering an effective education program. These responsibilities include setting goals and objectives of teaching and learning, and guiding students so that their efficiency in learning and other areas of the curriculum can be enhanced. Teachers' responsibilities include emphasizing on achieving goals and learning objectives, making decisions, organizing activities and working with other teachers to achieve set goals.

Hallinger et al. [9] show that the characteristics of a school actually have a profound impact to be taken into account in formulating successful leadership role models. The role of teacher leadership practiced by the teacher cannot only determine the achievement of a classroom goal but also affect all the individuals in the classroom. Teachers should undertake self-reflection, and carry out collaborative learning and problem solving in order to create an effective teacher leadership role.

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